

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Ancient Radiation Explains Most Conflicts Among Gene Trees and Well-supported Phylogenomic Trees of Nostocalean Cyanobacteria

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TABLE S1. Taxon sampling. Includes 216 taxa from the order Nostocales and four outgroup taxa from the order Chroococciopsidales. BUSCO scores were calculated using the “cyanobacteria_odb10” reference dataset, which includes 773 single-copy orthologs conserved across Cyanobacteria. To reduce dataset complexity for subsequent analyses, we selected a subset of 55 taxa (bold; part of subset 0) that include representatives from all major lineages that we identified on this initial phylogeny (Fig. S1). Strikethrough strains were not included in the phylogenetic analyses with 211 taxa (Fig. S1) due to low BUSCO completeness (< 89%).

Strain	Genome size (Mb)	% of complete and single-copy BUSCOs	Reference sequence accession	Assembly accession	Reference
<i>Anabaena cylindrica</i> PCC 7122	7.1	99.61	NC_019771	GCF_000317695.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Anabaena cylindrica</i> PCC 7122 v2	7.1	99.61	NZ_AP018166	GCF_002367955.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. 4-3	5.6	99.48	NZ_LUHJ000000000	GCF_001597745.1	Pfeffer et al. 2016
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. 90	5.3	99.22	NC_019427	GCF_000312705.1	Wang et al. 2012
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. AL09	4.7	98.06	LJOQ000000000	GCA_001672255.1	Driscoll et al. 2018
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. AL93	5.7	98.84	LJOU000000000	GCA_001672085.1	Brown et al. 2016
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. ATCC 33047	5.6	99.35	NZ_LUHI010000000	GCF_001597855.1	Pfeffer and Brown 2016
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. CRKS33	5	96.9	LJOT010000000	GCA_001672075.1	Driscoll et al. 2018
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. LE011-02	4.7	98.58	LJOP000000000	GCA_001672225.1	Driscoll et al. 2018
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. MDT14b	5	92.88	LJOV000000000	GCA_001672195.1	Driscoll et al. 2018
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. PCC 7108	5.9	99.48	NZ_AJWF010000000	GCF_000332135.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. WA102	5.8	98.84	NZ_CP011456	GCF_001277295.1	Brown et al. 2016
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. WA113	4.7	99.22	LJOS000000000	GCA_001672155.1	Driscoll et al. 2018
<i>Anabaena</i> sp. YBS01	7	99.48	NZ_CP034058	GCF_009498015.1	Negi et al. 2018. Unpublished
<i>Anabaena variabilis</i> NIES-23	7.6	99.74	NZ_AP018216	GCF_002368015.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Anabaenopsis circularis</i> NIES-21	7.2	99.74	NZ_AP018174	GCF_002367975.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Aphanizomenon flos-aquae</i> 2012/KM1/D3	5.7	77.36	JSDP000000000.	GCF_000789435.1	Sulcius et al. 2015

<i>Aphanizomenon flos-aquae</i> LD13	4.4	99.22	LJOY00000000	GCA_001672165.1	Driscoll et al. 2018
<i>Aphanizomenon flos-aquae</i> MDT14a	4.6	98.58	LJOX00000000	GCA_001672095.1	Driscoll et al. 2018
<i>Aphanizomenon flos-aquae</i> NIES-81	5.9	99.48	NZ_AZYY00000000	GCF_000521175.1	Cao et al. 2014
<i>Aphanizomenon flos-aquae</i> WA102	5.5	98.19	LJOW00000000	GCA_001672105.1	Driscoll et al. 2018
<i>Aulosira laxa</i> NIES-50	9.4	99.48	NZ_AP018307	GCF_002368055.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Calothrix brevissima</i> NIES-22	9.4	98.97	NZ_AP018207	GCF_002367995.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Calothrix desertica</i> PCC 7102	11.4	98.32	NZ_RSCL01000000	GCF_003991905.1	Will et al. 2019
<i>Calothrix desertica</i> PCC 7102 v2	11.4	98.32	NZ_VLKB00000000	GCF_007830875.1	Kerfeld et al. 2019. Unpublished
<i>Calothrix elsteri</i> CCALA 953	7.1	95.86	NZ_NTFS00000000	GCF_002289455.1	Gagunashvili et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Calothrix parasitica</i> NIES-267	9	98.45	NZ_AP018227	GCF_002368095.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Calothrix rhizosoleniae</i> SC01	5.9	97.8	FYBH00000000	GCF_900185595.1	Hilton et al. 2013
<i>Calothrix</i> sp. 336-3	6.4	99.74	NZ_CP011382	GCF_000734895.2	Isojärvi et al. 2015
<i>Calothrix</i> sp. NIES-2098	8.7	99.09	NZ_AP018172	GCF_002368175.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Calothrix</i> sp. NIES-2100	9.9	99.09	NZ_AP018178	GCF_002368195.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Calothrix</i> sp. NIES-2101 (HK-06)	9.7	98.06	NZ_MRCD01000000	GCF_001904745.1	Zhu et al. 2017
<i>Calothrix</i> sp. NIES-3974	6	99.09	NZ_AP018254	GCF_002368395.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Calothrix</i> sp. NIES-4071	11.1	98.32	NZ_AP018255	GCF_002368455.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Calothrix</i> sp. NIES-4105	11.1	98.32	NZ_AP018290	GCF_002368415.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Calothrix</i> sp. PCC 6303	7	99.48	NC_019751.1	GCF_000317435.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Calothrix</i> sp. PCC 7103	11.6	98.45	NZ_ALVJ01000000	GCF_000331305.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Calothrix</i> sp. PCC 7507	7	99.35	NC_019682	GCF_000316575.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Chlorogloeopsis fritschii</i> PCC 6912	7.8	98.06	NZ_AJLN01000000	GCF_000317285.1	Dagan et al. 2013
<i>Chlorogloeopsis fritschii</i> PCC 6912 v2	7.8	98.19	NZ_RSJ01000000	GCF_003990575.1	Will et al. 2019
<i>Chlorogloeopsis fritschii</i> PCC 9212	7.7	98.71	NZ_AJLM01000000	GCF_000317265.1	Dagan et al. 2013

<i>Chroococcidiopsis thermalis</i> PCC 7203	6.3	98.71	NC_019695	GCF_000317125.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Cuspidothrix issatchenkoi</i> CHARLIE-1	4.5	97.02	NZ_PGEM01000000	GCF_002934005.1	Kust et al. 2018
Cyanobiont of <i>Peltula cylindrica</i>	5.6	98.84	PRJNA918780 ^b	TO SUBMIT	McDonald et al. 2013 and this study
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> C03	3.9	98.71	NZ_NJHU01000000	GCF_002893155.1	Willis et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> C04	3.9	98.45	NZ_NJHT01000000	GCF_002893145.1	Willis et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> C07	3.9	98.71	NZ_NJHS01000000	GCF_002893125.1	Willis et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> CENA302	3.5	98.19	NZ_MTPU01000000	GCF_002027345.1	Abreu et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> CENA303	3.4	97.67	NZ_NBYN01000000	GCF_002114155.1	Abreu et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> Cr2010	3.5	98.32	NZ_PVMC01000000	GCF_003367075.1	Martin et al. 2019
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> CS-505	3.9	98.32	NZ_ACYA00000000	GCF_000175835.1	Stucken et al. 2010
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> CS-505 v2	3.9	98.71	NZ_LYXA01000000	GCF_001676585.1	Fuentes-Valdés et al. 2016
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> CS-508	3.6	95.21	NZ_MBQX01000000	GCF_001858115.1	Fuentes-Valdés et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> CYLP	4	75.55	NZ_NPIK01000000	GCF_002321935.1	Hoffmann et al. 2017
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> CYRF	4.2	82.15	NZ_NPIL00000000	GCF_002321945.1	Hoffmann et al. 2017
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> GIHE 2018	3.6	97.67	NZ_VHLJ01000000	GCF_006523545.1	Jeong et al. 2020
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> ITEP-A1	3.6	98.45	NZ_LUBZ01000000	GCF_001586755.1	Lorenzi et al. 2016
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> MVCC14	3.6	95.6	NZ_MBQY01000000	GCF_001858125.1	Fuentes-Valdés et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> S01	3.8	98.71	NZ_NJIA01000000	GCF_002893285.1	Willis et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> S05	3.8	98.58	NZ_NJHZ01000000	GCF_002893265.1	Willis et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> S06	3.8	98.71	NZ_NJHY01000000	GCF_002893245.1	Willis et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> S07	3.8	98.45	NZ_NJHX01000000	GCF_002893205.1	Willis et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> S10	3.8	98.32	NZ_NJHW01000000	GCF_002893215.1	Willis et al. 2018
<i>Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii</i> S14	3.9	98.06	NZ_NJHV01000000	GCF_002893185.1	Willis et al. 2018

<i>Cylindrospermopsis</i> sp. CR12	3.7	98.71	NZ_LMVE01000000	GCF_001432185.1	Nor et al. 2016
<i>Cylindrospermum stagnale</i> PCC 7417	7.6	99.48	NC_019757	GCF_000317535.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Dolichospermum circinale</i> AWQC131C	4.5	97.15	NZ_APIY00000000	GCF_000426905.1	D'Agostino et al. 2016
<i>Dolichospermum circinale</i> AWQC310F	4.4	97.28	NZ_APIZ00000000	GCF_000426925.1	D'Agostino et al. 2016
<i>Dolichospermum compactum</i> NIES-806	5.2	99.22	NZ_AP018316	GCF_002368115.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Dolichospermum planctonicum</i> NIES-80	4.6	99.35	NZ_BJCF01000000	GCF_005402965.1	Suzuki et al. 2019
<i>Dolichospermum</i> sp. UHCC 0315A	5.7	99.09	NZ_CP043056	GCF_008121535.1	Teikari et al. 2019
<i>Fischerella major</i> NIES-592	5.5	99.09	NZ_MRCA01000000	GCF_001904645.1	Zhu et al. 2017
<i>Fischerella muscicola</i> CCMEE 5323	6.8	98.97	NZ_NRQW01000000	GCF_002870665.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella muscicola</i> PCC 73103	7.6	98.19	NZ_AJLJ01000000	GCF_000317245.1	Dagan et al. 2013
<i>Fischerella muscicola</i> PCC 7414	6.9	99.35	AJLK01000000	GCF_000317205.1	Dagan et al. 2013
<i>Fischerella</i> sp. NIES-3754	5.8	99.22	NZ_AP017305	GCF_001548455.1	Hirose et al. 2016a
<i>Fischerella</i> sp. NIES-4106	6.2	98.84	NZ_AP018298	GCF_002368315.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Fischerella</i> sp. PCC 9339	8	98.06	NZ_ALVS01000000	GCF_000315585.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Fischerella</i> sp. PCC 9431	7.1	98.45	NZ_ALVX00000000	GCF_000447295.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Fischerella</i> sp. PCC 9605	8.1	94.05	NZ_ALVT00000000	GCF_000517105.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> 111/344/542	5.4	97.15	NZ_NGAA01000000	GCF_003346965.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> BR2B	5.3	99.22	NZ_NMQG01000000	GCF_002870705.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> CCMEE 5194	5.2	98.71	NZ_NQME01000000	GCF_002870795.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> CCMEE 5198	5.1	98.97	NZ_NMQF01000000	GCF_002870635.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> CCMEE 5201	6.7	98.19	NMQK00000000	GCF_002870785.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> CCMEE 5205	6.2	98.71	NZ_NMQJ01000000	GCF_002870745.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> CCMEE 5208	5.4	99.35	NZ_NMQH01000000	GCF_002870755.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> CCMEE 5268	5.9	98.71	NZ_NMQA01000000	GCF_002870565.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> CCMEE 5273	6.1	95.73	NZ_NMQB01000000	GCF_002870585.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> CCMEE 5282	5.3	97.02	NZ_NMQC01000000	GCF_002870615.1	Miller et al. 2020

<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> CCMEE 5318	6.2	97.41	NZ_NMQE01000000	GCF_002870675.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> CCMEE 5330	5.7	97.93	NZ_NMQI01000000	GCF_002870725.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> JSC-11	5.4	99.48	NZ_AGIZ00000000	GCF_000231365.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> PCC 7521	5.4	98.84	NZ_AJLL00000000	GCF_000317225.1	Dagan et al. 2013
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC1110	5.4	99.48	NZ_NGZS01000000	GCF_002870525.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC114	5.3	99.48	NZ_NGZU01000000	GCF_002870545.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC119	5.3	99.35	NZ_NGZT01000000	GCF_002870265.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC157	5.4	99.48	NZ_NGZV01000000	GCF_002870305.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC213	5.3	95.99	NZ_NHAK01000000	GCF_002870255.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC245	5.3	99.48	NZ_NHAI01000000	GCF_002870505.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC246	5.3	97.54	NZ_NHAH00000000	GCF_002870185.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC249	5.3	97.54	NZ_NHAG01000000	GCF_002870465.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC341	5.4	99.22	NZ_NGZW01000000	GCF_002870345.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC344	5.4	99.09	NZ_NHAF01000000	GCF_002870445.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC439	5.3	99.48	NZ_NHAE01000000	GCF_002870475.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC441	5.4	94.05	NZ_NHAD01000000	GCF_002870205.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC442	5.3	98.45	NZ_NHAC01000000	GCF_002870415.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC527	5.4	99.35	NZ_NHAB01000000	GCF_002870405.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC538	5.4	99.22	NZ_NHAA01000000	GCF_002870325.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC542	5.2	91.98	NZ_NGZZ01000000	GCF_002870385.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC558	5.2	98.58	NZ_NGZY01000000	GCF_002870365.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fischerella thermalis</i> WC559	5.2	98.19	NZ_NGZX01000000	GCF_002870195.1	Miller et al. 2020
<i>Fortiea contorta</i> PCC 7126	5.7	99.74	ANFJ00000000	GCF_000332295.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Fremyella diplosiphon</i> NIES-3275	8.9	99.22	NZ_AP018233	GCF_002368275.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Gloeocapsa</i> sp. PCC 7428	5.9	98.84	NC_019745	GCF_000317555.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Hapalosiphon</i> sp. MRB220	7.4	98.32	NZ_LIRN01000000	GCF_001275395.1	Tan et al. 2016
<i>Hassallia byssoidea</i> VB512170	13	97.93	NZ_JTCM02000000	GCF_000817785.2	Singh et al. 2015
<i>Mastigocladopsis repens</i> PCC 10914	6.3	99.22	ALVW01000000	GCF_000315565.1	Shih et al. 2013

<i>Mastigocladus laminosus</i> UU774	7	97.93	NZ_MNPM02000000	GCF_001990805.2	Panda et al. 2019
<i>Mastigocoleus testarum</i> BC008	12.7	60.8	NZ_LMTZ00000000	GCF_001456025.1	Guida et al. 2016
<i>Nodularia</i> sp. NIES-3585	5.8	99.22	NZ_BDUB01000000	GCF_002218065.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Nodularia spumigena</i> CCY9414	5.3	95.6	NZ_AAVW01000000	GCF_000169135.1	Voß et al. 2013
<i>Nodularia spumigena</i> CCY9414 v2	5.3	98.71	NZ_CP007203	GCF_000340565.2	Voß et al. 2013
<i>Nodularia spumigena</i> CENA596	5.2	97.93	NZ_LWAJ01000000	GCF_001623485.1	Popin et al. 2016
<i>Nodularia spumigena</i> UHCC 0039	5.4	98.97	NZ_CP020114	GCF_003054475.1	Teikari et al 2018
<i>Nostoc azollae</i> 0708	5.5	98.45	NC_014248	GCF_000196515.1	Ran et al. 2010
<i>Nostoc calcicola</i> FACHB-389	8.8	99.09	NZ_MRBZ01000000	GCF_001904715.1	Zhu et al. 2017
<i>Nostoc carneum</i> NIES-2107	8.4	99.48	NZ_AP018180	GCF_002368155.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc commune</i> NIES-4072	8.2	99.48	NZ_BDUD01000000	GCF_003113895.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc cycadae</i> WK-1	6.8	99.35	BDGE01000000	GCF_002897135.1	Kanesaki et al. 2018
<i>Nostoc flagelliforme</i> CCNUN1	8.4	98.19	NZ_CP024785.1	GCF_002813575.1	Shang et al. 2019
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> NIES-25	8.7	99.09	NZ_AP018222	GCF_002368035.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z1	9	98.84	NZ_LAGX01000000	GCF_002607965.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z13	9.2	97.15	NZ_LAHF00000000	GCF_002608275.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z14	9	98.19	NZ_LAHG00000000	GCF_002608345.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z15	9.6	98.06	NZ_LAHH00000000	GCF_002608385.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z16	9.9	97.93	NZ_LAHI00000000	GCF_002608325.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z18	8.9	98.45	NZ_LAHJ00000000	GCF_002607925.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z2	9	98.58	NZ_LAGY01000000	GCF_002607955.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z3	9	98.32	NZ_LAGZ01000000	GCF_002608015.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z4	9	98.58	NZ_LAHA01000000	GCF_002608075.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z6	9	98.71	NZ_LAHB01000000	GCF_002608105.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z7	9	98.32	NZ_LAHC00000000	GCF_002608135.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z8	9.1	98.19	NZ_LAHD00000000	GCF_002608145.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc linckia</i> z9	9	98.71	NZ_LAHE01000000	GCF_002608225.1	Zhou 2015. Unpublished

<i>Nostoc piscinale</i> CENA21	7.1	92.37	NZ_CP012036	GCF_001298445.1	Leão et al. 2016
<i>Nostoc punctiforme</i> PCC 73102	9.1	99.09	NC_010628	GCF_000020025.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. 106C	8.8	98.97	NZ_MTAW01000000	GCF_002154725.1	Gutiérrez-García et al. 2018
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. 3335mG	9.2	14.23	NZ_QHKA01000000	GCF_003185865.1	Gutiérrez-García et al. 2018
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. ATCC 53789	8.5	99.35	NZ_LWSY01000000	GCF_003326245.1	Tabuchi Yagui 2016. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. ATCC 53789 v2	8.7	99.35	NZ_CP046703	GCF_009873495.1	Tippelt et al. 2020
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. B (2019)	7.4	99.22	NZ_WVID01000000	GCF_010091925.1	Soares et al. 2020
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. CENA543	7.2	99.61	NZ_CP023278	GCF_002896875.1	Shishido et al. 2017
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Kroswia</i> sp. S13	7.4	97.93	JAQYWQ000000000	SAMN32648476 ^e	This study
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Lepidocollema</i> sp. S4	7.8	98.84	JAQYWR000000000	SAMN32648477 ^e	This study
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Leptogium austroamericanum</i> LPT	8.8	99.22	JABXKF000000000	GCA_017115165.1	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Lobaria pulmonaria</i> 5183	7.1	99.09	NZ_CP026692	GCF_002949795.1	Gagunashvili and Andresson 2018
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera aphthosa</i> JL23	8.2	99.22	JABXKN000000000	GCA_017115065.1	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera aphthosa</i> NOS	7.8	97.15	JABXKM000000000	GCA_017115025.1	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera dolichorhiza</i> NMS8	8.1	98.71	JABXKK000000000	GCA_017115045.1	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera evansiana</i> JL34	8	98.58	JABXKQ000000000	GCA_017114945	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera extenuata</i> JL31	7.8	98.71	JABXKO000000000	GCA_017114965	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera hydrothyria</i> NMS1	8	99.09	JABXKG000000000	GCA_017115145.1	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera hydrothyria</i> NMS2	7.7	99.22	JABXKH000000000	GCA_017115105.1	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera malacea</i> JL33	7.2	99.22	JABXKP000000000	GCA_017114985	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera membranacea</i> 210A	8.3	97.93	NZ_NOLJ01000000	GCF_002246015.1	Gagunashvili and Andresson 2018
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera</i>	8.3	98.19	NZ_NOLI01000000	GCF_002245975.1	Gagunashvili and

<i>membranacea</i> 213					Andresson 2018
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera membranacea</i> 232	9.2	97.67	NZ_NOLI01000000	GCF_002245985.1	Gagunashvili and Andresson 2018
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera membranacea</i> N6	8.2	98.71	NZ_CP026681	GCF_002949735.1	Gagunashvili and Andresson 2018
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera phyllidiosa</i> NMS9	8.2	98.45	JABXKL000000000	GCA_017114995.1	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Peltigera venosa</i> NMS4	7.7	94.57	JABXKI000000000	GCA_017115095.1	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Solorina crocea</i> NMS7	8.4	99.09	JABXKJ000000000	GCA_017115085.1	Cornet et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. DB3992	8.5	83.57	NZ_NSHF01000000	GCF_002631755.1	Gagunashvili and Andresson 2018
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. JC1668	7.6	99.09	NZ_SZNH01000000	GCF_005869855.1	Bell-Doyon et al. 2020
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. KVJ20	9.2	98.71	NZ_LSSA01000000	GCF_001712795.1	Halsør et al. 2019
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. NIES-2111	6.5	99.22	NZ_AP018184	GCF_002368215.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. NIES-3756	6.5	99.35	NZ_AP017295	GCF_001548375.1	Hirose et al. 2016b
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. NIES-4103	8.4	99.09	NZ_AP018288	GCF_002368335.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. PCC 7107	6.3	99.61	NC_019676	GCF_000316625.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. PCC 7120	6.4	99.61	NC_003272.1	GCF_000009705.1	Kaneko et al. 2001
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. PCC 7120 v2	6.4	99.61	NZ_RSCN01000000	GCF_003990585.1	Will et al. 2019
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. PCC 7524	6.7	99.74	NC_019684	GCF_000316645.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. RF31YmG	9.2	98.97	NZ_MTAX01000000	GCF_002155185.1	Gutiérrez-García et al. 2018
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. T09	8.3	99.09	NZ_MTAV01000000	GCF_002154695.1	Gutiérrez-García et al. 2018
<i>Nostoc</i> sp. UIC 10630	8.9	98.97	NZ_JAAGOG010000000	GCF_010747425.1	May et al. 2020
<i>Nostoc sphaeroides</i> CCNUC1	6.5	98.19	NZ_CP045226	GCF_009372195.1	Chen et al. 2021
<i>Nostoc sphaeroides</i> Kutzing En	6.5	98.45	NZ_CP031941	GCF_003443655.1	Cheng et al. 2018. Unpublished
<i>Nostocales</i> cyanobacterium HT-58-2	7.9	97.28	NZ_CP019636	GCF_002163975.1	Hughes et al. 2017
<i>Raphidiopsis brookii</i> D9	3.2	95.6	NZ_ACYB01000000	GCF_000175855.1	Stucken et al. 2010
<i>Raphidiopsis curvata</i> NIES-932	3.4	98.84	NZ_AP018317	GCF_002368135.1	Hirose et al. 2017.

					Unpublished
<i>Rhizonema</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Dictyonema</i> sp. 2651	8.1	90.94	JAQYWN000000000	SAMN32605760°	This study
<i>Rhizonema</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Dictyonema</i> sp. 3644	9.2	97.67	JAQYWO000000000	SAMN32605761°	This study
<i>Rhizonema</i> sp. cyanobiont of <i>Dictyonema</i> sp. 3668	9.1	87.58	JAQYWP000000000	SAMN32605762°	This study
<i>Richelia intracellularis</i> HH01	3.2	89.91	NZ_CAIY000000000	GCF_000350105.1	Hilton et al. 2013
<i>Richelia intracellularis</i> HM01	2.2	50.06	NZ_CAIS000000000	GCF_000350125.1	Hilton et al. 2013
<i>Richelia intracellularis</i> UBA3481	3.2	89.78	DFQU000000000	GCA_002377925.1	Parks et al. 2017
<i>Richelia intracellularis</i> UBA7409	3	84.73	DKMR000000000	GCA_002470035.1	Parks et al. 2017
<i>Rivularia</i> sp. PCC 7116	8.7	98.97	NC_019678	GCF_000316665.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Scytonema hoffmanni</i> PCC 7110	12.3	97.28	NZ_ANNX000000000	GCF_000346485.2	Dagan et al. 2013
<i>Scytonema hoffmanni</i> UTEX 2349 PCC 9009	8.2	98.71	ALWD010000000	GCF_000582685.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Scytonema millei</i> VB511283 ^a	11.6	98.19	NZ_JTJC000000000	GCF_000817735.3	Sen et al. 2015
<i>Scytonema</i> sp. NIES-2130 (HK-05)	9.3	98.06	NZ_MRCF010000000	GCF_001904675.1	Zhu et al. 2017
<i>Scytonema</i> sp. NIES-2130 (HK-05) v2	9.3	98.19	NZ_AP018194	GCF_002368235.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Scytonema</i> sp. NIES-4073	9.5	97.54	NZ_AP018268	GCF_002368435.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Scytonema</i> sp. UIC 10036	14.1	95.08	NZ_WJFC010000000	GCF_009725235.1	Crnkovic et al. 2020
<i>Scytonema tolypothrichoides</i> VB-61278	10	98.45	NZ_JXCA000000000	GCF_000828085.3	Das et al. 2015a
<i>Sphaerpermopsis reniformis</i> NIES-1949	6	98.06	NZ_BJCE010000000	GCF_005402885.1	Suzuki et al. 2019
<i>Sphaerpermopsis kisseleviana</i> NIES-73	5.4	99.09	NZ_AP018314	GCF_002368075.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Synechocystis</i> sp. PCC 7509	4.2	99.48	NZ_ALVU02000001	GCF_000332075.2	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Tolypothrix</i> sp. PCC 7910	8.5	99.35	NZ_CP050440	GCF_011769525.1	Song et al. 2020
<i>Tolypothrix bouteillei</i> VB521301	11.5	99.09	NZ_JHEG000000000	GCF_000760695.4	Chandrababunaidu et al. 2015
<i>Tolypothrix campylonemoides</i> VB511288	10.6	97.15	NZ_JXCB000000000	GCF_000828075.3	Das et al. 2015b
<i>Tolypothrix</i> sp. NIES-4075	8.4	98.97	NZ_BDUC010000000	GCF_002218085.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished

<i>Tolypothrix</i> sp. PCC 7601	10	99.22	NZ_AGCR00000000	GCF_000300115.1	Yerrapragada et al. 2015
<i>Tolypothrix tenuis</i> PCC 7101	8.7	99.48	NZ_AP018248	GCF_002368295.1	Hirose et al. 2017. Unpublished
<i>Trichormus</i> sp. NMC-1	5.9	98.97	NZ_LZQD01000000	GCF_001858025.1	Qiao et al. 2016
<i>Trichormus variabilis</i> 0441	6.4	99.74	NZ_CP047242	GCF_009856605.1	Mikheeva et al. 2019. Unpublished
<i>Trichormus variabilis</i> ATCC 29413	6.4	99.87	NC_007413	GCF_000204075.1	Shih et al. 2013
<i>Trichormus variabilis</i> PCC 6309 (SAG 1403-4b)	6	98.84	NZ_RSCM01000000	GCF_003991935.1	Will et al. 2019
<i>Wetiellopsis prolifica</i> IICB1	7.2	97.93	NZ_NAPS01000000	GCF_004323185.1	Verma et al. 2017

^aThis strain is classified in Genbank as Nostocales, but our phylogenetic analyses placed it within the order Chroococciopsidales (Fig. S1).

^bBioproject accession.

^cBiosample accession.

TABLE S2. Pseudolikelihood scores for the networks inferred with SNaQ with different h values.

We selected $h = 2$ as the best network.

h	Pseudolikelihood score
0	386.433
1	293.488
2	219.072
3	194.964
4	0.0

FIGURE S1. Phylogeny of all 211 taxa included in this study. This is a maximum likelihood tree inferred with the concatenated L746 dataset (Table 1) of amino acid sequences using default parameters in RAxML v8.2.12 (Stamatakis 2014). Outgroup taxa belong to the order Chroococcidiopsidales. The 55 taxa selected for subset 0 (Table S1) are shown in bold. Note that the *Nodularia* “clade” is paraphyletic.

We included *Nostoc* sp. NIES-4103 in the *Nodularia* group as a reference for our analyses of conflict because several other analyses recover it as monophyletic (e.g., Fig. 2). Support values are shown only for branches with bootstrap < 100 and length > 0.001 substitutions per site.

FIGURE S1 (continued).

FIGURE S1 (continued).

FIGURE S2. Mean UFBoot values of gene trees inferred from a) nucleotide, and b) amino acid L1648+ng alignments with different number of variable sites. The horizontal dashed lines indicate the UFBoot value of the inflexion point of the curve fitted to the datasets. The vertical dashed lines are located at 100 variable sites. The gene alignments on the upper right quadrant relative to the dashed lines constitute the a) L1082 and b) L1233 sets (see Materials and Methods).

FIGURE S3. Summary of alignment features for loci set L1648 before and after trimming with different strategies (Table 1). a–d) Amino acid alignments. e–f) Nucleotide alignments. Prop. missing; proportion of missing data in the alignment matrix. PSI: parsimony-informative sites.

FIGURE S4. Model selection for amino acid alignments. Bars show the difference in Bayesian Information Criterion inferred for the best site-homogeneous ($BIC_{\text{site-hom.}}$) and the best site-heterogeneous ($BIC_{\text{site-het.}}$) substitution model for each amino acid alignment in the L1648+ng set. Green: site-heterogeneous model fits data better; orange: site-homogeneous model fits better.

FIGURE S5. Convergence among the three chains (c1–c3) run for divergence time estimation with MCMCTree. Each point on the plots corresponds to the mean posterior age inferred by each chain for each of the 11 nodes of the major-edge tree in Fig. 4a. a) Chain 1 compared to chain 2. b) Chain 1 compared to chain 3. c) Chain 2 compared to chain 3.

FIGURE S6. Effect of gene sampling and methodological choices on phylogenetic conflicts based amino acid datasets (Table 1). Boxplots show percentages of gene trees that are concordant (a, d, g; blue), discordant (b, e, h; red), and uninformative (c, f, i; grey) for each topological bipartition of the concatenated dataset tree inferred with the same set of genes. For example, each data point included in the leftmost box of panel a) corresponds to the percentage of gene trees from the L31+ng set that is concordant with one of the bipartitions in the concatenated dataset tree inferred with the L31+ng alignment set. Trees in a–f) were inferred with site-heterogeneous models (aa site-hete), and trees in g–i) were inferred with site-homogeneous models (aa site-homo). Panels a–c) show comparisons among sets of loci, and panels d–i) show comparisons among alignments of the same loci trimmed with different strategies (Table 1). We used 95% UFboot as support threshold to assess conflict. None of the categories were significantly different (ANOVA $p > 0.05$). The results of the analyses with nucleotide datasets are shown in Figure S6.

FIGURE S7. Effect of gene sampling and methodological choices on phylogenetic conflict based on nucleotide datasets (Table 1). Boxplots show percentages of gene trees that are concordant (a, d; blue), discordant (b, e; red), and uninformative (c, f; grey) for each topological bipartition of the concatenated dataset tree inferred with the same set of genes. For example, each data point included in the leftmost box of panel a) corresponds to the percentage of gene trees from the L31+ng set that is concordant with one of the bipartitions in the concatenated dataset tree inferred with the L31+ng alignment set. Panels a–c show comparisons among sets of loci, and panels d–f show comparisons among alignments of the same loci trimmed with different strategies (Table 1). None of the categories were significantly different (ANOVA $p > 0.05$). We used 95% UFboot as support threshold to assess conflict.

FIGURE S8. Fully supported topologies (where all internodes were highly supported with UFBoot > 95 %) inferred with concatenated phylogenomic jackknifed data sets (Fig. 5c and f). a) Anomaly zone subtrees. b) Outside anomaly zone subtrees. A: *Cylindrospermum stagnale* PCC7417, Ni: *Trichormus variabilis* ATCC 29413, Nii: *Nostoc* sp. cyanobiont of *Peltigera apthosa* JL23, No: *Nodularia* sp. NIES 3585, F: *Fortiea contorta* PCC 7126, Fi: *Fischerella* sp. PCC 9605, O: *Chroococciopsis thermalis* PCC 7203 and Cyanobiont of *Peltula cylindrica*, Ri:

Rivularia sp. PCC7116, S: *Scytonema* sp. NIES-2130 (HK-05) v2, and T: *Tolypothrix* sp. NIES 4075.

FIGURE S9. ASTRAL tree inferred with gene trees from the L1648+ng+aa+site-het dataset. Branch lengths represent coalescent time, with shorter internodes indicating higher conflict

among gene trees. Support values are posterior probabilities. Only posterior probabilities < 1 are shown.

FIGURE S10. Phylogeny of all 211 taxa included in this study. This is a maximum likelihood tree inferred with the concatenated L1648+ng dataset of nucleotide sequences and the 16S rRNA gene. Outgroup taxa belong to the order Chroococcidiopsiales. The 55 taxa selected for subset 0 (Table S1) are shown in

bold. Support values are shown only for branches with UFBoot < 100 and length > 0.001 substitutions per site.

FIGURE S10 (continued).

FIGURE S10 (continued).

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